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The most common among inflammatory periodontal diseases is generalized periodontitis (GP), which is a kind of dystrophic-inflammatory process resulting from the combined exposure to various exogenous and endogenous factors.

According to most researchers, HP is a polyetiological disease, the development of which is based on a complex of pathological changes occurring in the oral cavity associated with microbiological, immunological changes against the background of the existing genetic predispositions [12].

Etiological factors of periodontal diseases traditionally divided into local and systemic. Local include those that act directly in periodontal tissues, then as systemic depend on the general condition of the patient. The most important local factor of etiopathogenesis is considered to be bacterial colonization of the cervical surface of the teeth in the form of "bacterial

GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS AND METABOLIC SYNDROME. UNITY OF PATHOGENETIC DEVELOPMENT MECHANISMS

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ABSTRACT

Current periodontal disease represents a complex problem that acquires not only medical, but also social significance. It's connected before with a high prevalence and intensity of periodontal tissue damage [4]. A high incidence of periodontitis, the severity of some forms of periodontal pathology, loss teeth and as a result significant changes in dentition, decrease in working capacity, decrease in the quality of life of the population – all this makes it possible to consider periodontal diseases not only a serious medical, but also an important social problem.

plaques", invasion of microbes into periodontal tissue with release of various inflammatory mediators, proteolysis factors [1]. This "aggression of pathogens", according to many authors, in itself does not mean the inevitable development of periodontal disease. The probability of developing the disease is ultimately determined by a number of local and systemic factors.

Numerous studies have established that the occurrence of significant functional and morphological changes in the periodontal complex is facilitated by universal pathogenetic mechanisms that are formed in various diseases of organs and systems.

The relationship between general somatic diseases and the state of the oral cavity organs is due to metabolic disorders, hemodynamics, microcirculation, immunological and neuroregulatory changes and shifts in microbiocenosis. Diseases that cause direct impact on the

condition of the periodontium in patients, are primarily diabetes mellitus, diseases of the cardiovascular system, chronic respiratory diseases and osteoporosis [7]. The rapid increase in the incidence of newly diagnosed type 2 diabetes is now time is one of the most important public health problems in developed countries. Data from a recent large meta-analysis showed that more than half of Europeans suffer from hyperglycemia and/or diabetes mellitus in the course of life [9].

The main components of MS are: obesity, insulin resistance, dyslipidemia and arterial hypertension. The basis of the formation MS is an IR that triggers a cascade of metabolic disorders and contributes to the development of various pathological conditions. In most cases, the initiating moment of the occurrence of IR is overweight, which, in turn leads to the development of arterial hypertension and a decrease in the sensitivity of peripheral tissues to insulin, followed by progressive accumulation of excess weight body. The most pathogenic in the development of MS is abdominal type of obesity [2,6]. It is the rise amount of visceral fat is associated with hyperinsulemia. Leading pathogenic mechanisms in implementations of MS components are activation inflammatory factors, endothelial dysfunction, disruption of fibrinolysis processes, changes in procoagulant activity of blood plasma, oxidative stress, pronounced immunological shifts, disorders of autonomic nervous regulation, which are implemented at the level of various organs and systems. Most of the pathophysiological manifestations of a complex of metabolic disorders, closely related to insulin resistance intertwined with leading pathogenetic links in the

development and progression of generalized periodontitis.

Adipose tissue is a multifunctional organ responsible not only for the deposition of fat, but also for the production of numerous biologically active molecules, such as estrogens, cytokines, angiotensinogen, inhibitor plasminogen activator-1, lipoprotein lipase, adiponectin, interleukin-6 (IL-6), tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), transforming growth factor B, leptin and others. Adipokines regulate tissue homeostasis, energy cell costs, glucose levels, and inflammation. The metabolic syndrome is characterized by a state of chronic mild inflammation, accompanied by an increase in the production of adipocytes of the adipose tissue pro-inflammatory cytokines, including IL-6, TNF- α , and CRP by the liver [3,5]. The inflammatory-dystrophic process in the periodontium is accompanied by hypoxia of periodontal tissues, which leads to the activation of free-radical oxidation processes. Activation of free radical oxidation is considered as a mechanism adaptation of the organism to changes in the level of oxygen in tissues. The result of free radical oxidation is the formation of active forms oxygen. Generation of reactive oxygen species in tissues normally induces the synthesis of protective systems: antioxidants and other protective systems. Against the background of the metabolic syndrome, a number of mechanisms are realized that lead to endothelial dysfunction. On the one hand, it is the activation of pro-inflammatory factors, including cytokines, C-reactive protein. On the other hand, activation of lipolysis in the fat cell, leading to the release of lots of free fatty acids active synthesis of lipoproteins very low density, which triggers a number

of lipid metabolism disorders. Adipose tissue hormones regulate the same production of a number of vasoactive agents, including angiotensin - II, prothrombogenic factors. Formed by the influence of these mechanisms inflammatory lesion of the vascular endothelium channels against the background of dyslipidemia characteristic of IR, leads to endothelial dysfunction and early atherosclerosis. Endothelial dysfunction is manifested by a violation of endothelium-dependent vasodilation and an increase in thrombotic properties of the endothelial lining of blood vessels. It has been proven that oxidized LDL have a high toxicity, reduce the ability of vascular endothelium to produce nitric oxide, an endothelium-dependent relaxation factor, which is accompanied by relatively excessive production of vasoconstrictor factors - endothelin-1 and angiotensin, activation of apoptosis of vascular cells. Reduced oxide production characteristic of IR nitrogen forms hypersensitivity vascular wall to the action of vasoconstrictors substances, the processes of endothelium-dependent vasodilation are disrupted [10]. In the pathogenesis of microcirculation disorders in patients with GP, an important role belongs to disorders in the vascular-platelet and coagulation links of the hemostasis system, fibrinolysis system, rheological properties of blood. Violations in microcirculatory link of hemostasis are caused by changes in the processes of activation and aggregation platelets and endothelial thrombosis resistance vascular wall. With an increase in the severity of HP, the process of activation and aggregation of platelets increases, antiaggregation, anticoagulant activity decreases. Disorders of the hemostasis system in this category of

patients develop according to the type of disseminated intravascular coagulation. The state of IR is also accompanied by pronounced microcirculatory disorders, changes in antiaggregation, anticoagulant and fibrinolytic properties of the vascular endothelium. The earliest structural and functional changes in MS are found at the level of peripheral vessels. All components of the microcirculation system are involved in the pathological process. Remodeling at the microvascular level includes rarefaction of the vascular bed, changes in the media/lumen ratio, slowing down neoangiogenesis, dysfunction of the endothelium [8]. Most studies that have studied the relationship between MS and the state of bone tissue have been devoted to the problem of postmenopausal metabolic syndrome in women. It has been shown that MS, in combination with ovarian hypofunction, is associated with disorders of calcium-phosphorus metabolism and secretion of calcium-regulating hormones, decreased mineral density of bone tissue, suppression of osteoformation processes with preserved bone resorption [14].

The state of bone tissue in men with manifestations of MS has not been studied enough. A number of recent studies demonstrate close relationship between atherosclerosis and osteoporosis, which is relevant in patients with MS, characterized by a high proatherogenic potential. Free radical oxidized lipids able to inhibit the development of osteoblasts and bone formation, disrupt the differentiation of progenitor cells not into osteoblasts, but into adipocytes. Inflammatory mediators that promote atherogenesis in the vascular wall, in bone tissue stimulate the release of substances

by osteoblasts, promoting osteoclastogenesis [15]. Several cytokines, including IL-6 and TNF, play a role in the regulation of osteoclast function. Shown that lipoprotein cholesterol levels are low density (LDL) is significantly inversely proportional to bone mineral density. The effect of leptin and adiponectin, secreted by adipose tissue, on the state of bone tissue is being actively studied. At there is currently no consensus on the relationship between blood leptin levels and weight bone tissue. There was only a moderate association with bone alkaline phosphatase and more pronounced - with bone mass and obesity. Elevated leptin levels were associated with increased concentrations of a number of bone matrix proteins. There is evidence

that leptin, which is associated with the development of obesity in metabolic syndrome, can inhibit the process of bone formation [11,13].

Features of the state of metabolic processes in the bone tissue of the alveolar ridge against the background of MS, the relationship with changes in inflammation indicators, leptin levels are practically not studied. Thus, the presence of MS, as a condition with a high risk of developing diabetes, creates prerequisites for the formation of inflammatory-destructive lesions of the periodontium, as evidenced by the commonality of a number of pathogenetic mechanisms for the development of these diseases.

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